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Resonant silicon nanoparticles for efficiency and stability enhancement of perovskite solar cells

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Abstract. A lot of attempts were given to improve efficiency of lead halide perovskites solar cells in last several years by chemically active plasmonic nanoparticles implementation, but there is no data about stability in time. To solve both problem we added low-loss and chemically inert resonant silicon nanoparticles between electron transport layer and perovskite layer that allows to increase not only efficiency enhancement via improved light harvesting, photocurrent, open-circuit voltage and fill-factor, but also we increase these characteristics in few days after device preparation. Silicon nanoparticles allow achieve the device efficiency up to 18.8%, being a record among the previously reported results on nanoparticles incorporation into $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ (MAPbI_3) perovskite-based solar cells. The proposed method of efficiency enhancement can be used for solar cells with various chemical compositions of perovskites.

1. Introduction

Nowadays lead halide perovskite solar cells (PSCs) are an extremely prospective class of energy sources due to high power conversion efficiency, low cost of materials and simple solution processing for their fabrication [1, 2]. To increase light harvesting from thin perovskite film of SC and produce more charges plasmonic nanoparticles (PNPs) incorporation is used as one of the common methods. Also, it allows to increase PSC photocurrent and efficiency via increase of nonradiative decay of excitons improving charge separation. However, this approach allowed to achieve efficiency up to 18.2% and fill factor up to 75.5% for record device based on the most popular and well-studied methyl ammonium lead iodide perovskite (MAPbI_3) [3, 4]. At the same time, noble metals are expensive and chemically unstable in halide perovskites. There is no work devoted to the study of efficiency behavior in time for PSCs included metallic NPs.

Meanwhile, resonant silicon nanoparticles were recently proposed for a number of applications [5, 6], where its optical losses as compared with plasmonic counterparts and strong Mie resonances were employed for local field enhancement and effective scattering

power pattern manipulation. Regarding implementation of silicon nanoparticles (NPs) for perovskites based devices, high enough optical contrast of silicon ($n > 3.5$) with halide perovskite ($n > 2.2$) would enable the excitation of Mie resonances in visible range resulting in effective light trapping at nanoscale [7].

To increase absorbance by photoactive perovskite layer, enhance efficiency of PSCs and protect devices from fast degradation we for the first time incorporated resonant Si NPs to n-i-p structure MAPbI₃-based PSCs with mesoporous electron-transport layer (m-ETL).

2. Discussion

Silicon NPs were prepared by laser ablation procedure to achieve polycrystalline structure with negligible SiO₂ layer on the surface (Figure 1 a). Figure 1b – 1b.1 shows the n-i-p device structure and photograph for a completed SC. A 50-nm TiO₂ compact layer is deposited on top of a back tin oxide (FTO) electrode. An m-TiO₂ presents a m-ETL has a 200-nm thickness, capped by photoactive MAPbI₃ perovskite (150/350 nm). The 400-nm hole transport layer (HTL), SPIRO-OMeTAD, doped with Bis(trifluoromethane)sulfonimide lithium salt, coats perovskite, and 80-nm gold layer, was deposited as a top contact. The Si NPs, located between m-TiO₂ and perovskite, have size between 50 and 180 nm. This Si NPs location allows to keep device morphology from thickness change or additional layers roughness.

Figure 1. a) TEM image of individual silicon NPs. b, b.1) The photograph of completed device and their layer scheme.

To check the reproducibility of improvement a set of 30 devices (one half is reference, another part contain Si NPs) originated by two independent batches of production were considered. All PSCs (with and without NPs) show an efficiency higher than 15%, which indicates a standard state of art fabrication process for MAPbI₃ based PSCs. The champion reference device showed a PCE of 17.7% whereas the best cell with Si NPs performs 18.8%. As shown in Fig. 2, the presence of Si NPs clearly increases the average and the best efficiency of the cells with respect to that without NPs that is related to an increase of J_{SC} (+1.8%), FF (2.4%), and V_{OC} (+1%). It should be noted that the V_{OC} and J_{SC} boost is an indicator of nanoantenna effect of devices from Si NPs [8].

Figure 2. The statistical data of main photovoltaic parameters for PSC: a) efficiency, b) shunt current density, c) open-circuit voltage and d) fill factor for the reference cells (black) and for cells with Si NPs.

As an additional effect we have observed that the presence of Si NPs improves some photovoltaic characteristics as shown in figure 3. After preparation, the PSC were left in air conditions humidity of about 30%. While the average PCE of PSCs without NPs slightly decrease after 4 days of shelf life, the PCE of PSCs with Si NPs increases with time that is not observed before for devices contained plasmonic NPs. This observation can argue that since this improvement of PCE mostly comes from improvement of FF, the series resistance R_{SER} is decreased in presence of Si-NP with shelf time of 4 days. Since Si-NP are quite big (100-200 nm) with sizes comparable to grains in perovskite layer, and of same scale as thickness of perovskite layer itself, one can expect that with time the morphology of the interface between $MAPbI_3$ and Si-NP surface become less strained and less defective, with less grain boundaries (which usually create resistance for transport) improving thus the sheet resistance in bigger grains around Si-NP, and thus overall improved FF. Better morphology of perovskite grains rearrangement around Si-NP can also lead to less leakages and shorts around grains adjacent to Si-NP, this effect increasing shunt resistance, which also improves FF with time. It can be also explained by the slow coalescence of perovskite crystallites around Si-NP during time periods at the scale a few days or weeks after device performance as mentioned by Roose for mixed perovskite [9].

Figure 3. Statistical data of main photovoltaic parameters: total efficiency (a), short-circuit current density (b), open-circuit voltage (c) and fill factor (d) for some perovskite devices with (grey) and without (black) silicon NPs measured again after 4 days from preparation time.

3. Conclusion

To sum up, we increase efficiency and stability of perovskite solar cells by Mie-resonant Si NPs, which improve light harvesting to increase photocurrent and positive affect on fill factor and stability of perovskite layer.

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